

DIGITAL DERMATOGLYPHICS IN IJAW STUDENTS OF UNIVERSITY OF PORT HARCOURT, NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT

This study was done on the digital print patterns of the Ijaw ethnic group using the students of University of Port Harcourt, Nigeria. The digital prints of 450 students comprising 250 males and 200 females were collected with the use of ink pads. These patterns were recorded and classified using standard methods. The result showed the Ulnar loop pattern having the highest frequency (45.2%) on all the fingers in both sexes, closely followed by the Whorl pattern (32.6%) then the Arch pattern (14.28%) the least in occurrence was the Radial loop pattern (7.4%). There was no significant difference between the sexes ($P>0.05$). The Ijaw males also showed greater difference in print pattern between the two hands than the females. This study has confirmed findings in other ethnic groups in Nigeria.

KEY WORDS: Dermatoglyphics, ulnar loop, whorl pattern, ijaw

INTRODUCTION

The scientific study of the papillary ridge of the hands and feet (dermatoglyphics) is credited as beginning with the work of Joannes Evagelista Purkinje (Gyenis 2000). He systematically categorized the finger print patterns into a nine pattern classification.

The skin ridge are never duplicated in two persons even in monozygous twins but similarities have been found in the same ethnic groups and variation noted in different ethnic groups and races Danknierjer (1947) Harrich *et al* (2002). In Nigeria several studies have been published on the dermatoglyphic patterns in some ethnic groups Ogunranti and Sorgia (1984),Igbigbi *et al* (1994),Danborno and Idris(2007) and Osunwoke *et al* (2008)

A number of diseases such as Diabetes Mellitus (Oladipo and Ogunowo 2004; Barta *et al* 1978), Sickle cell disease (Oladipo *et al* 2007), Breast cancer (Seltzer *et al* 1990), Obesity (Regoly-Merci *et al* 1982), Rheumatoid Arthritis (Ravindranath *et al* 2006) Schizophrenia (Gyenis *et al* 1990) have all been reported to have characteristic dermatoglyphics patterns. The work by Ogunranti and Sorgia (1984) revealed that the ulnar loop had the highest percentage frequency among the people of Ogoni in Bodo, Southern Nigeria, this was corroborated by Osunwoke *et al* 2008 on the ikwerre and Okrika natives in the same region of Nigeria and by Danborno and Idris (2007) on the Hausas in the northern part of the country, the percentages however differ.

The study by Odokuma and Igbigbi (2005) on the students of Delta State University, Abraka, Nigeria observed that the loops had the highest frequency of occurrence in the thumbs in both sexes. The females had more arch patterns than the males while the whorls occurred more in the males. Studies in other parts of Africa have also revealed characteristic and similar dermatoglyphic patterns like that of the Nigerians though with differences in percentages (Igbigbi and Msamati 1999, 2001) Jantz *et al* (1982)

These studies have clearly demonstrated that even within the same geographical area, dermatoglyphic patterns though similar differ in proportions.

The aim of this study was to determine the dermatoglyphic patterns of the students of the University of Port Harcourt of Ijaw ethnic group. The Ijaw people make up the major ethnic group of the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was carried out in the University of Port Harcourt, Port Harcourt Nigeria in 2008. A total number of 450 students age ranging from 20 – 24 years comprising 250 males and 200 females were studied. These students were normal and healthy. All the subjects had both parents and grandparents of Ijaw origin.

Digital ink prints of all the fingers of both hands in each subject were taken and studied with the aid of a magnifying glass. The prints were analyzed based on Cummins method (Cummins and Mildo 1929;1943). Data was presented as mean and percentage frequencies. Differences between the male and female ridge patterns in both hands were tested for significance using the student 't' testss Prabhakara (2006).

RESULTS

Tables 1 & 2 showed the percentage frequency distribution of the digital patterns in the right hand. The ulnar loop occurred most frequently on the third finger in both sexes. It was indeed the most frequently occurring in both sexes followed by the whorl pattern, the arch pattern, the least was the radial loop pattern. The fifth finger of both hands in the males did not have any radial loop.

Table 3 showed the total percentage occurrence in all the ten fingers in both sexes. The ulnar loop print pattern was 46.4% in the males and 44% in the females followed by the whorl pattern with 30.6% in the males and 32.75% in the females.

The females had more radial loops (9%) while for the arches, the males had a total of 14.8% and the females 13.75%. The differences noted in the two sexes were not significant (P>0.05). The difference noted between the right and left digital prints was also not significant (P>0.05).

Table 1: Percentage frequencies of the Digital patterns of the left hand of both male and female students of Ijaw origin.

Patterns	Males					Females				
	Digits					Digits				
	i	ii	iii	iv	v	i	ii	iii	iv	v
Ulnar loop	36	40	50	40	44	45	42.5	47.5	40	55
Radial loop	16	12	8	6		7.5	10	10	10	10
Whorl	30	34	32	36	42	35	30	30	35	22.5
Arch	18	14	10	18	14	2.5	17.5	12.5	15	12.5

Key

i Left hand – thumb, ii Left hand- 2nd digit, iii Left hand -3rd digit, iv - Left hand -4th digit, v Left hand -5th digit

Table 2: Percentage frequencies of the Digital Patterns of the right hand of both male and female students of Ijaw origin.

Patterns	Males					Females				
	I	ii	iii	iv	v	I	ii	iii	iv	v
Ulnar loop	48	44	56	42	64	45	45	37.5	50	57.5
Radial loop	4	4	4	4		10	12.5	15	5	7.5
Whorl	34	28	26	38	30	30	27.5	27.5	37.5	25
Arch	14	24	14	16	6	15	15	20	10	10

Key

i Right hand – thumb, ii Right hand- 2nd digit, iii Right hand -3rd digit, iv Right hand -4th digit
v Right hand -5th digit

Table 3: Total percentage frequency of digital print patterns of the students of ijaw origin in the University of Port Harcourt.

Print Patterns	Sex (%)			
	Ulnar loop	Radial Loop	Whorls	Arches
Male	46.4	5.8	30.6	14.8
Female	44	9	32.75	13.75
M+F	45.2	7.4	31.68	14.28
	P>0.05			

Key

M + F = Males and Females

DISCUSSION

The data obtained and the analysis of the digital print patterns of the students of Ijaw origin at the University of Port Harcourt, Nigeria is in keeping with the findings of earlier workers in Nigeria and other parts of the World (Cummins 1926; Borroface 1978; Odokuma and Igbigbi 2005 and Osunwoke *et al* 2008). The ulnar loop pattern had the highest frequency in both sexes followed by the whorl pattern, the arch and lastly the radial loop pattern. It was noticeable that the males had a higher percentage of the ulnar loop pattern and arch pattern while the females had higher percentage in the whorl pattern and the radial loop. This difference though not significant (P>0.05) is worthy of mention. The total loop pattern of all the ten fingers (radial and ulna) gave a higher percentage to the females at 53% and males at 51.2%. Comparing the thumb print pattern, the females had a higher percentage (45%) in the left hand as against 36% in the males while for right hand the males had slightly higher percentage 48% than the females (45%).

The total percentage of the loop patterns (ulnar + radial) in the thumb print in our study was 52% for males and 53.75% for females. This corroborates a similar study by Odokuma and Igbigbi(2005) who also recorded a higher percentage of loop patterns for females, our work showed a much lower percentage of whorl pattern of the thumb print being 32.0% and 32.50% respectively for males and females unlike what was observed in their study where they had 46.75% and 43.07% respectively for males and females. The arch pattern, in their study was however much lower at 4.34% and 6.10% compared to ours at 16.0% and 13.75% for males and females respectively.

The frequency recorded for the arch pattern (14.28%) of all the fingers in our study was quite different from the report of the Igbos of the South East Nigeria (12.50%) by Igbigbi *et al* (1994) but closely equates with that of the

Okrika ethnic group of the same Niger Delta region as the Ijaws with 14.12 (Osunwoke *et al* 2008) and markedly different from that of the Hausas with 6.62% as reported by Danborno and Idris (2007).

The level of difference between right and left digital prints was higher in the Ijaw men than the women, this could well imply that the developmental disturbances resulting in fluctuation asymmetry (Blabber (1991), Burton *et al* (2003), was more in the male Ijaws contrary to the study on the Hausas where the asymmetry between the right and the left hand was more in the females (DanBorno and Idris 2007). The male Ijaws also did not have any radial loop pattern of digital print in the little finger of both hands.

CONCLUSION

This study has shown that the digital finger print patterns of students of Ijaw origin in the University of Port Harcourt share a close similarity with those of other ethnic groups in Nigeria and also of Africans. Jantz *et al* (1982), Boroffice (1978), Igbigbi and Msamati (1994). No two finger prints were the same as was also seen by our study corroborating with all the earlier authors.

This study also has shown that dermatoglyphics can not be used for sex identification in a particular ethnic group. It is however relevant in anthropology and genetics especially in the identification of the ethnicity of a particular individual or group of people.

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